

Bachelor's Degree in Computer Engineering

EI1048 – Software Paradigms

SEMINAR 2

REPORT

Authors

Author 1	Author 2
Author 3	Author 4

Selected generative AI tool

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Initial User Story Proposal (include the prompt submitted to the AI)

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Assessment of the Initial Proposal (Item 4, maximum 9–10 lines)

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Proposed Changes to the Initial User Story Set (item 5)

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Justified Proposal of User Stories for the 3-Month App Release

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Identified User Profiles (evaluate the profiles; indicate the selected one)

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Final Reflections on the Activity (item 11)

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